

Stress Analysis of a Splice Joint of the Wing and Fatigue Life Estimation under Variable Loading

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Abstract – This paper studies the large stress induced part of the splice joint in the bottom wing skin of an aircraft due to tensile loading and its fatigue life estimation. The aero foils attached to each side of the fuselage produce lift force. These aero foils are called wings and joints in aero foils and fuselage are inevitable. The surface of the wing needs smooth surface to reduce drag force. Thus the smooth surface of aero foils is obtained by splice joint between skin plates. This research investigates the part of an aerofoil with splice joint in a bottom skin for stress analysis. The splice joint considered in this research is associated with several spar beams, ribs and stiffeners with skin plate covered around it. In this research the chord-wise splice joint of aerofoil skin is focused for stress analysis. The splice joint is riveted on multiple rows which experiences the action of tensile in plane load due to wing bending. The finite element analysis of the joint is carried out to find the stresses at rivet joint holes due to By-pass load, bearing load and secondary bending. The stress analysis is performed to evaluate the stresses around rivet holes. Analyses were performed by MSC PATRAN and NASTRAN software. The analysis revealed that the rivet joints region experience the maximum stress. The most stress concentrated part was identified by local finite element analysis of a splice joint. The maximum stress concentrated part was considered for fatigue life calculations by S-N curve method. The fatigue life of the joint and the crack initiation period is evaluated under a real service load values by local stress-strain approach.

Keywords: Aircraft, Wing, Stress analysis, Splice joint, Finite Element Analysis, Fatigue, S-N curve method and stress-strain approach

I. Introduction

The ideal flight vehicle structure would be the single complete unit of similar material involving one manufacturing operation. Unfortunately this cannot be achieved in practical because the every portion of aircraft structure involves numerous numbers of parts and the unavailability of material for required span. So joints cannot be avoided in aircraft structure.

Splice joints are normally used to provide a smooth aerodynamic surface of the skin for the aircraft structural components. The aero foils are major parts which produce lift to the aircraft. The aero foils differ in design based upon the type and purpose of aircraft. The wing box (i.e. aerofoil) generally consists of two kinds of joints, i.e. spar splice joint & skin splice joint. The inboard and outboard portions of top and bottom skins are joined together by means of skin splice joint. The inboard and outboard spars of front and rear side are joined by the means of spar splice joint. The spar beams resist most of the bending moment occurred on the wing and the shear force is reduced by smooth skins.

In this research the splice joint on chord-wise direction of wing skin is focused for a finite element analysis. The splice joint is riveted on multiple rows under the action of tensile in plane load caused by wing bending. The

simple loads acting on aircraft is necessary to understand the wing bending. The aircraft structure experience the following loads,

(i) Weight (ii) Lift (iii) Drag (iv) Thrust

Weight: Weight is a force that is always directed toward the centre of the earth. The resultant magnitude of the weight depends on the mass of the entire aircraft parts, the fuel in fuel tank and payload on board, if any.

Lift: The opposition force to overcome the weight force, which is generated by airplanes, is called lift. Lift is produced by the motion of the aircraft through the air and is an aerodynamic force. "Aero" means the air, and "dynamic" means motion. Lift is produced on perpendicular direction to the flight direction.

Drag: When an aircraft flies on air, there is another aerodynamic force also generated. The air repels the motion of the aircraft and the opposition force is called as drag force.

Thrust: To overcome drag force, an airplane contains a propulsion system to produce a force called thrust force [2].

I.1. Wing and Wing Box

Wing is the important structural unit of an aircraft and it is going to bend during flying due to lift load acting in it. So that the wing skin on bottom side is subjected to tensile load and top wing skin is subjected compressive load [4]. The most of the forces on wings arise when the plane is airborne. Since the wings need to support the entire weight of the aircraft the steady stresses are more, and with the wings of the aircraft bending upwards, the upper surfaces of wing skin in compression and the bottom side in tension. Because of this tension force the tensile stress concentration will be more on the joints of bottom side wing skin of the aircraft.

This research focuses the middle portion of the wing with riveted splice joint at the bottom skin, which is called wing box. This part of wing box consists of two spar beams (C-section), three numbers of ribs (I-section), four numbers of L-shaped stiffeners at top of ribs and four numbers of rectangular shaped stiffeners at bottom of ribs. The bottom and top portions of this box are covered with wing skin which is a thin sheet.

The skin sheet on the top side is designed as the integrated part with the wing box. The skin on bottom side is designed in two pieces and they are joined by splice plate. The bottom flange of the middle rib is designed as the splice plate of the joint. The bottom wing skin and splicing plate is joined by rivets. The wing box is unsymmetrical in its all axes. The wing box parts and dimensions have been selected by the aerodynamic calculations which have the CFD (computational fluid dynamics) procedure. These calculations reveal the thicknesses of spar beams (3 mm), ribs (2 mm), skin (1.5 mm) and stiffeners (4 mm).

Fig. 1: CAD model of Wing box (CATIA V5R19)

II. Experimental Details

II.1. Finite Element Analysis using MSC PATRAN/NASTRAN

Stress analysis was done in two stages. The first stage is global analysis which involves the analysis of complete structure taken for analysis to identify the stress concentrated portion at splice joint of the bottom wing skin. The next stage is the finite element analysis of the splice joint alone with 26 Multi Point Constructed (MPC) rivet holes and it is called local analysis. The MPC's were used to allow the stress flow in required direction and arrest the stress flow in other directions.

In global analysis the IGES model of the wing box structure was imported from the design software CATIA V5R19 to FEA software MSC-PATRAN for geometry extraction. The major parts of wing box i.e. spar, ribs, stiffener plates and the skin is meshed separately. The triangular and quadratic elements are used to mesh this model, because of their lower stiffness properties. The beam elements were used for rivet connections.

The portion near the cut-out region of stiffener the fine discretization was done and the coarse mesh was done for the rest of the portions of wing box. The loads, boundary conditions and material properties, were applied to the discretized wing box to find the stress concentration at wing box. The discretized model of wing box is shown in figure 2(a).

Fig. 2(a) Meshed model of wing box

In local analysis the splice joint alone has been modeled by MSC PATRAN which is the maximum stress concentrated part. The length of the splice joint taken for this analysis is 210mm and the skin plate is 180mmx210mm with the 50mm height web. The thickness of the bottom skin, splice plate and web plate in this analysis are same as in the wing box. The holes of rivet is 5mm for the joint which are made by MPC's and the rivet connection has been provided to the joint using one dimensional beam elements. The result of this analysis gives the exact stress concentration at splice joint, since we have used the real rivet holes with fine meshing around the joint.

II.2. Software used for Stress Analysis

PATRAN - Pre-processor and Post processor
NASTRAN - Solver

II.3. Calculations of Loads

The total weight of the aircraft considered for the analysis is 2000 kg.(4-seater aircraft)
The total weight of the aircraft = 2500 kg.
Design load factor considered= 3g.
The total load on the aircraft = 2500×3
Total load = 7500kg
The Factor of safety considered =1.5
The total design load = 7500×1.5
The design load = 11250kg

The lift force experienced by fuselage and wing.
 The Lift force on the wing = 80% of total load=
 0.8×11250
 Lift load on the wing = 9000kg
 The load acting on each wing = $9000/2 = 4500$ Kg

The entire span of the wing and the wing box (portion shown in dark line) dimensions with resultant load are shown in figure 2(b)

Fig. 2(b) Wing box dimensions with load.

The load of the resultant is acting at a distance of 2000 mm (from aerodynamic calculations) from the wing root.
 The maximum Bending Moment at the wing root = $4500 \times 2000 = 9.0 \times 10^6$ kg-mm
 The B.M at the root of the wing box = $4500 \times 1060 = 4.77 \times 10^6$ kg-mm
 The load at tip of the wing box = $4.77 \times 10^6 / 1560 = 3057$ kg.
 This 3057 kg load is converted into UDL and distributed at tip of the wing box in bending direction of wing.

II.4. Boundary Conditions and Loads

The UDL of 1.03 kg/mm was distributed at tip side of the wing box and other end is fixed i.e. root side. A two dimensional linear static stress analysis is performed using the software MSC PATRAN and MSC NASTRAN. Mesh independent stress values are attained through repetitive mesh refinement. Aluminium 2024-T351 alloy material properties are given to the Pre-processor MSC PATRAN. Load corresponding to the maximum lift force on the wing is considered to be applied on wing box.

In local analysis the 6.135 kg/mm of UDL was distributed at the tip of the splice joint and the other end was fixed. The load was calculated from the stress state around the splice joint in the wing box stress analysis.

III. Results and Discussions

The boundary conditions and loads applied to the wing box structure are shown in figure 3(a).

Fig. 3(a) wing box loading conditions

The distribution of stress for the applied loads was observed and that shows the stress is distributed uniformly but major stresses are developed near the rivet joint area of the bottom skin splice joint. The most stress concentrated part of the wing box i.e. bottom wing skin splice joint is shown in below figure 3(b)

Fig. 3(b) Maximum stress concentrated part of bottom skin splice joint.

Fig.3(c) Maximum stress generated at rivet holes of the splice joint plate

From the figure 3(a), 3(b) and 3(c) it was observed that maximum stress of the wing box structure is concentrated near the rivet joint hole locations of the splice joint of the bottom wing skin. The local stress analysis of the joint with boundary conditions and loads are shown in figure 3(d)

Fig. 3(d) local analysis on splice joint

The local analysis result gives the exact stress values at the elements on the rivet joint hole region. The maximum stress is concentrated near the riveted holes obtained by the given load 6.135 kg/mm, is $\sigma_{max} = 29.8 \text{ kg/mm}^2$. The figure 3(e) gives the maximum stress in red color.

Fig. 3(e) Maximum stress near splice joint rivet hole.

And these regions will be fatigue critical locations in the aircraft bottom wing skin.

IV. Fatigue Life Estimation using S-N Curve Approach

Fatigue is the continuous and localized damage of the structure that happens when a material is exposed to repetitive loading. Fatigue occurs in lower stress state also when a material is imposed to the cyclic loading. If the applied loads are more than yield strength of the material, microscopic level cracks will form at the surface. Since the fatigue develops structural damage at lower stress cases, the fatigue calculations of the selected structure are very essential for the safety concerns. In this research the fatigue life to initiation of crack of the stress affected part of the splice joint is focused for fatigue life calculation. The deterioration made by every cycle is calculated by reference to the material life curve, in this case the S-N curve. The S-N curve shows the approximate numbers of cycles to failure, N_f , for a applied stress range, S . The figure 4(a) shows the S-N curve for wing box material Aluminium 2024-T351.

The total destruction instigated by N cycles is therefore obtained as the ratio of cycles to the number of cycles to failure.

Fig. 4(a) S-N curve for Aluminium 2024-T351

The Palmgren-Minor rule can therefore be expressed in (1).

$$Accumulated\ Damage = \sum_i \frac{N_i}{N_f} \quad (1)$$

Where, N_i is the no. of cycles with a particular stress range and mean; i -is a variable range covering all the possible range and the mean combination values; and N_f is the no. of cycles to failure for a selected stress range and mean. The total damage is provided as a proportion of the damage needed to fail the selected material. Therefore the total fatigue life of the component can be found from Equation (1). The total damage is experimentally found to be between 0.7 and 2.2. Usually for design purposes, it is assumed to be 1.

TABLE I
LOAD SPECTRUM VALUES FOR FATIGUE CALCULATION

g' condition	stress in 'Mpa'	Number of cycles
0.5g to 0.75g	22.78	45000
0.75g to 1.0g	22.78	30000
1.0g to 1.25g	22.78	25000
1.25g to 1.5g	22.78	20000
0g to 1.75g	159.49	30
0g to 2.0g	182.26	1
-0.5g' to 1.5g	182.26	100

In this research the testing of the Al 2024-T351 wing box material has been conducted for the input conditions as given on the table 1 and the load spectrum was also generated. The corresponding stress values were calculated for the selected “g” conditions. Here as usual the designer considers '1g' is equal to the all-up weight of the aircraft.

The fatigue life of the structure is infinite, if the no. of cycles to failure is more than 10^7 cycles. Here maximum stress value attained from the stress analysis at the rivet hole location of the joint is 182.26 Mpa. But the fatigue failure occurs at 200 Mpa and above stress ranges (refer figure 4.a). So the fatigue will not affect the splice joint analyzed in this paper.

V. Conclusion

The bottom wing skin splice joint portion has been identified as the maximum stress concentrated part for the stress analysis. FEA approach is selected for the stress analysis. Boundary conditions and loads are accurately simulated to obtain the response of the wing box similar to actual wing structure. Maximum stress of $\sigma_{max} = 29.8 \text{ kg/mm}^2$ is obtained at bottom wing skin splice joint rivet hole. The maximum tensile stressed location is the portion of fatigue crack initiation spot in the wing box. Using these results the fatigue life of the part to crack initiation calculations have been done by S-N curve approach. The fatigue calculations revealed that the bottom wing skin splice joint will not fail by fatigue.

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